

THE IMPORTANCE OF COMMUNICATIVE SPEECH IN IMPROVING THE PEDAGOGICAL TRAINING OF FUTURE EDUCATORS

Jabborova Marifat Qodiraliyevna

Teacher of the Department of Social and Humanitarian Sciences of Fergana State University

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Abstract. *This article discussed the need for developing communicational dialogue ability, design of the object of pedagogical communication, the development of relations with family and other social partners.*

Keywords: *communicative speech, communicative purpose, information exchange, interactive purpose, perceptual purpose.*

Introduction

The level of pedagogical skills of the teacher, his communicative skills, psychological readiness to establish appropriate relationships with the child in the process of upbringing and education, on the one hand, ensure the high efficiency of the upbringing and education process, on the other hand, the preschool educational organization ensures the safety of the educational environment.

The effectiveness of the preschool education system directly depends on the level of the educator's communication skills, the child's ability to adequately perceive, accept, understand and support the teacher's speech. The established communicative speech style helps to effectively implement educational and educational tasks, to successfully establish a trusting relationship between the teacher and the child.

The teacher's problem of communicative speech Abulkhanov-Slavskaya, Bazylevich T.F., V.A. Goryanina, M.I. Studied by Stankin. The essence of communicative speech in harmony with pedagogy was described by A.N. Leontiev, B.T. Likhachev, G.K. Selevko, P.M. Ershov, E.N. Ilyin, S. Yu. Scholars such as the Hills have considered. Features of professional and pedagogical communicative speech S.N. Batrakova, V.A. Also, it was the focus of Tolochek's works.

Considering the problems of pedagogical communicative speech is one of the most important tasks today, because the development and upbringing of children is carried out in the process of communicative speech with highly qualified specialists. Communicative speech is one of the most common categories described in philosophical, social and psychological-pedagogical literature. Also, in modern psychology, there are different opinions about the nature of the communicative speech process. A number of psychologists (Ch. Osgurd and others) consider communicative speech to be an interpersonal process consisting of exchanging information and giving someone something (for example, knowledge, social experience, etc.). Basically, communication here means the process of transmitting and receiving information. According to another approach (M. Argyle, T. Shibutani, etc.), communication is understood as information exchange and interaction. From the point of view of many local studies, it can be argued that the concept of "communicative speech" cannot be fully revealed only through the categories of "communicative speech" and "interaction". The process of communicative speech accompanies our whole life, in everyday situations, a person engages in active communicative speech for one

reason or another. Communicative speech can be conditionally divided into informative and purposeful.

Informative communicative speech is the main motive of communication, information exchange. Purposeful communicative speech is related to the implementation of professional activities. Thus, we can come to the conclusion that the communicative speech of the future teacher in his professional activity is always purposeful communication.

Based on this, professional communication is between an employee and a person engaged in his professional activities, including responsibility for their implementation, conditioned by professionally important goals, directly or by one means or another. The process of establishing indirect communication and supporting communicative speech is understood.

Also, professional communicative speech is multifunctional according to its content and purpose. From a psychological point of view, the following signs of professional communicative speech are distinguished:

- communicative purpose - exchange of information between its carriers;
- interactive goal - interaction of participants in professional communication;
- perceptual goal is to perceive professional information.

The content of the concept of development of the preschool education system until 2030 is aimed at solving the problem of providing equal initial opportunities for preschool children to enter school. The future educators of the preschool educational organization have a special influence on the development of the child's personality, because they contribute to the realization of the child's creative development and self-improvement. Accordingly, it is suggested to pay attention to the following principles of working with children when preparing future educators for their pedagogical activities:

- use of systematic and project organization of educational content;
- wide use of methods that activate children's ability to search;
- forming a children's team, etc.

The main condition for the development of the preschool education system is the training of pedagogical staff with professional training. In this regard, the following is necessary for the preparation of future educators for their pedagogical activities:

- to update the content of psychological-pedagogical training of specialists in higher education institutions in order to form the need-motivation sphere in the development of the professional thinking of future educators;

- to prepare students for pedagogical activity to the extent that they are able to work in the conditions of interpersonal relationships, know the methods and methods of organizing pedagogical work with children, taking into account the characteristics of different models of preschool education;

- to provide conditions for future teachers to grow creatively, work on themselves, improve their qualifications and pass certification in time.

Thus, to create the necessary conditions to achieve the modern quality of training students for pedagogical activity, to develop technologies aimed at changing the internal position of the future teacher, his value-semantic definition, as the main condition for the adoption and development of new pedagogical ideas need

In this regard, the issue of providing students with theoretical and practical knowledge, as well as improving the pedagogical training of future teachers based on a comprehensive approach, is one of the least studied and problematic issues, which is explained by the following:

- firstly, the conflicting methodological approaches and concepts of development of preschool children prevailed at different historical stages of the history and development of preschool education, as well as the professional competence of educators;

- secondly, educators' idea that the development of preschool children should be based on a systematic model of education in the same type of educational organizations.

The analysis of modern scientific research shows that the work under consideration mainly focuses on the problems of professional education. It was found that there are not enough studies aimed at improving the pedagogical training of future teachers based on a comprehensive approach in higher education.

It was found that there are a number of shortcomings in improving the pedagogical training of future educators:

- the goals of improving the pedagogical training of future teachers are not formed by employers, but are determined in the process of teaching in higher education;

- Pedagogical training of future educators does not meet the needs of preschool education and special types of preschool education organizations;

- the teaching technologies and methods of higher education in improving the pedagogical training of future educators do not always meet modern requirements;

- existing forms of teaching in the pedagogic higher education system have all their advantages as well as disadvantages: episodic learning, insufficient attention to the integrity and individuality of the process of formation of professional competence;

- the integration of science, education and production also affects the main functions of the teaching system in higher education, its main functions include: compensatory, adaptive, corrective, developmental, innovative, integrative. The fact that the most common forms of teaching in pedagogic higher education institutions are aimed not at developing professional competence, but at increasing the level of theoretical knowledge.

The implementation of new requirements in the system of training future educators for pedagogical activity in higher education is seen in the formation of new principal constructors of the educational principle: competencies and metaprofessional qualities. The inclusion of these constructors in the teaching content means that knowledge and skills will be transferred to the level of tactical educational units, and competences and skills will become strategic concepts. With a wide range of uses, such constructors have a clearly defined practice-oriented, activity-oriented direction, which really ensures the competitiveness of professionals.

A study aimed at organizing a system of training future teachers for pedagogical activities directed at the modern needs of preschool education was conducted, and the important signs, structure, criteria and indicators of the student's professional competence were determined in the study:

- assessment of the formation of professional competencies required by the preschool education organization in future teachers (development of competencies, effective competencies, high efficiency competencies); creating a competency model;

- development of professional competence of future educators in the process of implementing educational programs and teaching methods based on a comprehensive approach;

- analysis of the impact of improving the preparation of future educators for pedagogical activities on the development of preschool children.

Results

It is important for future educators to develop such skills as solving problem situations, working with professional information, implementing professional self-development, and implementing a holistic pedagogical process in accordance with the specific characteristics of the preschool education organization. is considered

Discussion

-that it is necessary to develop the ability to communicate, design an object of pedagogical activity, organize interactions with family and other social partners;

-the need to evaluate the effectiveness of the object of pedagogical activity, to develop the ability to choose the forms, methods and means of educating preschool children;

-the need for the development of methodological support, the creation of a professional career and the skills of managing the types of activities of preschool children.

The criteria for the effectiveness of research results were considered in two cases:

- firstly, the criteria of effectiveness in preparing future educators for pedagogical activities are related to the results of educators expressed at the level of qualification;

- secondly, the efficiency criteria in preparing future educators for pedagogical activities are related to the influence of the level of educators' qualifications on the results of pedagogical activities expressed as children's education.

We identified the following as indicators of the readiness of future educators to develop their professional competences in the preparation of pedagogical activities:

- a high level of motivation to change professional pedagogical activity in preparing future educators for pedagogical activities;

- adaptation of future educators to changes in the professional pedagogical environment (restructuring of their activities in connection with the emergence of changes in preschool education and the expansion of the variability of educational services);

- future teachers' ability to communicate in solving pedagogical situations; setting changing and complex goals of professional-pedagogical activity and searching for ways to solve them by planning pedagogical tasks;

- the ability of future teachers to acquire new professional competencies, to update the forms and methods of pedagogical activity;

- the ability of future educators to analyze their professional and pedagogical activity and to reconstruct it based on the development of new educational and scientific information;

It became known that the training process for preparing future teachers for pedagogical activities in the higher education system today has the following possibilities:

- to quickly update the content of providing theoretical knowledge and educational technologies to prepare future educators for pedagogical activities;

- taking into account the needs of educators of the future preschool education organization and different levels of development of their professional competences;

- unification of personnel and methodological resources;

- unification of scientific research, educational design and information-analytical activities.

Conclusion

By using the above-mentioned possibilities of the educational process in preparing future teachers for pedagogical activities in higher education, the profession of a teacher of a preschool educational organization will gradually move into the category characterized by the highest level of mobility.

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